

MEDDOPROF Supplementary Materials

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Abstract. This document is a companion to the article ‘NLP applied to occupational health: MEDDOPROF shared task at IberLEF 2021 on automatic recognition, classification and normalization of professions and occupations from medical texts’ which includes more information on the Gold Standard annotations and the results of all submitted runs.

Keywords: shared task · clinical domain · occupations · Spanish.

A Occupation Typology

The MEDDOPROF corpus provided a diversity and variability of mentions referring to professions and working statuses for people of all ages, including mainly texts generated by clinicians working in Spain, but also covering some cases from Latin America (to address the issue of language variants). The included clinical cases describe multiple health situations: from common diseases, workplace accidents, exposure to harmful substances, mental health-related issues to substance abuse and others. The psychiatry case reports were particularly comprehensive in their description of the schooling and work history of patients. The annotations in the corpus are also really varied, both in form and content. This implies that the resulting systems should generalize well across various clinical specialities and language variants, but it also increases the difficulty of the posed MEDDOPROF track. In this section, an overview of the different types of occupations is given.

Direct mentions. The simplest type of annotation are direct mentions that use job titles, which many times includes one-word occupations, as in examples 1 and 2.

1. ‘Paciente varón, de 55 años, **albañil** de profesión, casado [...]’
‘55-year-old male patient, works as a **construction worker**, married [...]’
2. ‘Su trabajo como **taxista** le lleva a pasar muchas horas fuera de casa.’
‘Their work as a **taxi driver** makes them spend many hours away from home.’

Descriptive mentions. The language used throughout the corpus documents can be quite descriptive (as in example 3), which leads to some longer annotations:

3. ‘El paciente **refirió trabajar en el aeropuerto vendiendo flores** [...]’
 ‘*The patient reported working in the airport selling flowers.*’

There are certain patterns which are quite frequent, such as references to a speciality (or lack thereof; see examples 4, 5) or to the workplace (example 6). Sometimes, both are referenced at the same time (example 7).

4. ‘Se trata de un hombre de 55 años de edad, **dedicado desde hace 45 años al campo y la alfarería.**’
 ‘*[The patient is] a 55-year-old man, working in the farming and pottery industry for 45 years.*’
5. ‘[...] **está contratado en un trabajo sin cualificación** que no le reporta satisfacción.’
 ‘*[The patient] is hired in an unskilled job that does not bring him satisfaction.*’
6. ‘Desde los 18 **trabaja en un negocio familiar, un pequeño hotel** situado en las afueras de Madrid [...]’
 ‘*Since age 18, they work in a family business, a small hotel located on the outskirts of Madrid [...]*’
7. ‘**Ha trabajado en diversos locales del sector de la hostelería.**’
 ‘*[They] have worked in different places in the hospitality sector.*’

From a linguistic point-of-view, many descriptions are performed through verb or preposition phrases (see examples 8, 9), as well as longer noun phrases (example 10), that explain or allude to an occupation.

8. ‘La paciente **abandonó su puesto de trabajo** y fue tratada con corticoides durante 6 meses.’
 ‘*The patient quit her job and was treated with corticosteroids for 6 months.*’
9. ‘[...] después de un año consiguió otro **en un taller de torno.**’
 ‘*A year later, they found another [job] in a lathe workshop.*’
10. ‘Paciente [...] que ha trabajado como **dueño de explotación agrícola y ganadera.**’
 ‘*Patient [...] who has worked as a farm and livestock owner.*’

A somewhat common formula (that is probably a consequence of the clinical domain’s writing style being quite reductive at times) is for occupations to be introduced by a short title or header (as in examples 11 and 12). Additionally, as it often happens with clinical texts, there are multiple abbreviations that add complexity to the corpus and require at least some familiarity with the domain. For instance, in example 13 ‘MAP’ means ‘médico de atención primaria’ (*Primary Care physician*), ‘CTS’ means ‘corticoides’ (*corticoids*) and ‘ATB’ means ‘antibióticos’ (*antibiotics*).

11. ‘**Historia Laboral: fábrica de aluminio.**’
 ‘*Work history: aluminium factory.*’
12. ‘**Ocupación: hogar.**’
 ‘*Occupation: home.*’

13. ‘[...] refiere varios cuadros de infecciones respiratorias anuales junto con disnea tratadas por su **MAP** con CTS y ATB de amplio espectro.’
 ‘[...] *[The patient] reported multiple annual respiratory infections along with dyspnea treated by their **PCP** with CS and ATB.*’

Variety of employment statuses. In terms of specific labels, employment statuses are particularly interesting. Other than the usual ones (e.g. ‘unemployed’, ‘retired’), we tried to include a wide range of situations that are related to or have some kind of impact in occupations. For instance, current/finished studies (see example 14) or different types of work settings (example 15).

14. ‘**Ha cursado la ESO** con grandes dificultades y es usuaria de lengua de signos.’
 ‘*[She] has finished secondary school with great difficulty and is a sign language speaker.*’
15. ‘[...] su esposa, una maestra de escuela, y su hijo de 21 años, desarrollador web, también **trabajaban desde el hogar**.’
 ‘[...] *his wife, a school teacher, and his 21-year-old son, a web developer, also worked from home.*’

Additionally, the employment status tag includes multiple socioeconomic situations relevant to the occupational status: homelessness (example 16), imprisonment (example 17), people who are not receiving any kind of wage (example 18), ... All of these contribute an important social element to the corpus.

16. ‘Las fugas del domicilio han sido constantes, volviendo a **situación de calle** y abandono completo del autocuidado’
 ‘*[They] frequently escaped from their home, returning to a homeless situation and a complete abandonment of their self-care.*’
17. ‘El paciente se encuentra actualmente **en Centro Penitenciario** por incumplimiento de la orden de alejamiento [...]’
 ‘*The patient is currently in prison for breaching the restraining order [...]*’
18. ‘Hace 6 años que **no trabaja, sin percibir subsidio** alguno.’
 ‘*[They] haven’t worked in six years, receiving no pay whatsoever.*’

Activity label. The activity label, which includes non-paid occupations, is one of the most varied despite being the least common. Some mentions include references to non-professional sport activities (see examples 19, 20), as well as more general hobbies (examples 21, 22).

19. ‘Realiza de forma regular ejercicio físico **saliendo a correr** con el padre’
 ‘*[The patient] exercises regularly and goes running with their father.*’
20. ‘El paciente **acude al gimnasio de rehabilitación** en silla de ruedas’
 ‘*The patient goes to the rehabilitation gym in a wheelchair.*’
21. ‘Además, señalaba que **le gustaba realizar actividades de jardinería** en su domicilio.’
 ‘*Additionally, [the patient] pointed out that they liked doing gardening activities at home.*’

22. ‘Había estado expuesto al sol puesto que va al monte a diario (es **cazador**) pero llevaba medidas de protección y sombrero’
*‘[The patient] had been exposed to the sun since he goes to the mountains daily (he is a **hunter**), but he uses protective measures and a hat.’*

Ambiguous mentions. An important point is that the distinction between paid and non-paid occupations causes some mentions to be ambiguous. For instance, the occupation ‘cuidador’ (*caregiver*) can be a paid occupation or a role taken up by a family member. In the former case, they were classified as a profession (see example 23); in the latter, they were classified as an employment status (see example 24).

23. ‘El paciente vive con una **cuidadora** y tiene 8 hijos que van a visitarlo con frecuencia.’
*‘The patient lives with a **caregiver** and has 8 children who visit him frequently.’*
24. ‘La paciente indica ser la **cuidadora principal** de su madre, una mujer de 98 años de edad.’
*‘The patient points out that she is her mother’s **main caregiver**, who is a 98-year-old woman.’*

Ambiguity is also somewhat frequent in the second annotation axis (patient, family member, ...). Even if most of the health-related occupations refer to health workers involved in the patient’s treatment and diagnosis, there are some cases in which the patient or a family member is a health worker (examples 25 and 26, respectively).

25. ‘Varón de 46 años, **médico anestesista** de profesión, que acude por primera vez a consulta de Atención Primaria [...]’ // *‘46-year-old male, who works as a **anaesthetist doctor** and comes to Primary Care consultation for the first time [...]’*
26. ‘Destacamos una sobrina, hija de la hermana del paciente, que es **enfermera** y con la que tiene buena relación [...]’
*‘We’d like to point out that the patient has a niece, his sister’s daughter, who is a **nurse** and with whom he has a good relationship [...]’*

B Complete Results

This section compiles the results of all of the runs submitted to the MEDDO-PROF shared task, divided by sub-task and sorted from higher to lower F1-score.

Table 1. MEDDOPROF-NER results. Submissions with an asterisk (*) had a formatting error.

Team Name	System	Precision	Recall	F-score
NLNDE	Splits	0.855	0.783	0.818
NLNDE	All	0.847	0.783	0.814
NLNDE	Domains	0.851	0.777	0.812
MUCIC	Flair-BERTembedding	0.813	0.788	0.8
NLNDE	Transfer	0.838	0.766	0.8
SMR-NLP	BiLSTM-CRF	0.854	0.751	0.799
NLNDE	Clinic	0.825	0.762	0.792
SINAI	multiclassbeto	0.821	0.74	0.778
SINAI	enhancedbinary	0.788	0.72	0.752
Vicomtech NLP-team	meddoprof-joint	0.758	0.739	0.748
SINAI	binarybeto	0.787	0.707	0.745
Fadi	BERT Transformers 4	0.802	0.678	0.735
URJC	BETO Finetuned	0.765	0.706	0.734
Fadi	BERT Transformers 5	0.807	0.657	0.724
Fadi	BERT Transformers 1	0.781	0.671	0.722
Fadi	BERT Transformers 2	0.785	0.659	0.717
Fadi	BERT Transformers 3	0.755	0.673	0.711
TALP	default	0.761	0.645	0.698
gbali	CRF	0.786	0.586	0.671
TALP	extended	0.67	0.67	0.67
galiza	lookup_rules+custom_spacy	0.731	0.597	0.657
EdIE-KnowLab	BETO_Positive	0.585	0.712	0.643
TALP	no_fine_tune	0.665	0.615	0.639
KaushikAcharya	CRF	0.807	0.524	0.635
MUCIC	BERT	0.809	0.515	0.629
galiza	custom_spacy	0.834	0.469	0.6
EdIE-KnowLab	BETO_Positive_ProfNER	0.535	0.657	0.589
IITKGP	Domain-specific BERT	0.654	0.5	0.567
galiza	lookup_rules	0.745	0.455	0.565
ICC	BETO_0906	0.741	0.435	0.549
ICC	NaiveEnsemble	0.765	0.412	0.536
EdIE-KnowLab	BETO_ALL_ProfNER	0.718	0.425	0.534
EdIE-KnowLab	BETO_ALL	0.685	0.433	0.53
	Baseline	0.465	0.508	0.486
HULAT-UC3M	MeaningCloud	0.412	0.53	0.464
ICC	BETO_0306	0.69	0.349	0.463
ICC	BETO_0406	0.746	0.32	0.448
ICC	BETO_0906_2	0.684	0.295	0.412
HULAT-UC3M *	Hulat	0.067	0.536	0.12
HULAT-UC3M *	BETO	0.002	0.014	0.003

Table 2. MEDDOPROF-CLASS results

Team Name	System	Precision	Recall	F-score
NLNDE	Splits	0.83	0.759	0.793
NLNDE	All	0.83	0.757	0.792
NLNDE	Transfer	0.819	0.743	0.779
NLNDE	Clinic	0.816	0.74	0.776
NLNDE	Domains	0.806	0.737	0.77
MUCIC	Flair-BERTembedding	0.77	0.75	0.764
SMR-NLP	BiLSTM-CRF	0.802	0.699	0.747
SINAI	multiclassbeto	0.775	0.69	0.73
Vicomtech NLP-team	meddoprof-joint	0.71	0.691	0.701
Fadi	BERT Transformers 4	0.761	0.644	0.698
Fadi	BERT Transformers 1	0.743	0.638	0.687
Fadi	BERT Transformers 3	0.728	0.648	0.686
URJC	BETO Finetuned	0.71	0.664	0.686
Fadi	BERT Transformers 5	0.761	0.618	0.682
Fadi	BERT Transformers 2	0.747	0.626	0.681
TALP	default	0.694	0.588	0.637
TALP	extended	0.628	0.627	0.627
gbali	CRF	0.726	0.538	0.618
EdIE-KnowLab	BETO_ALL	0.604	0.603	0.604
MUCIC	BERT	0.77	0.488	0.598
SINAI	enhancedbinary	0.593	0.541	0.566
TALP	no_fine_tune	0.588	0.544	0.565
SINAI	binarybeto	0.592	0.531	0.56
EdIE-KnowLab	BETO_Positive	0.455	0.631	0.529
ICC	BETO_0406	0.662	0.377	0.48
ICC	NaiveEnsemble	0.711	0.356	0.474
ICC	BETO_0306	0.667	0.303	0.417
	Baseline	0.391	0.377	0.384
ICC	BETO_0906.2	0.678	0.231	0.345
ICC	BETO_0906	0.65	0.214	0.322

Table 3. MEDDOPROF-NORM results

Team Name	System	Precision	Recall	F-score
TALP	default	0.675	0.572	0.619
Fadi	BERT Transformers 5	0.682	0.541	0.603
Fadi	BERT Transformers 3	0.654	0.557	0.602
Fadi	BERT Transformers 1	0.656	0.544	0.595
Fadi	BERT Transformers 4	0.658	0.543	0.595
TALP	extended	0.594	0.591	0.592
galiza	lookup_rules+custom_spacy	0.72	0.482	0.577
galiza	lookup_rules	0.744	0.458	0.567
TALP	no_fine_tune	0.591	0.544	0.567
KaushikAcharya	CRF	0.72	0.467	0.566
	Baseline	0.502	0.533	0.517
Fadi	BERT Transformers 2	0.569	0.47	0.515
SINAI	binarybeto	0.685	0.404	0.508
SINAI	enhancedbinary	0.679	0.404	0.507
galiza	custom_spacy	0.84	0.359	0.503
Vicomtech NLP-team	transformer_system	0.488	0.474	0.481
ICC	NaiveEnsemble	0.567	0.388	0.461
ICC	BETO_0306	0.517	0.361	0.425
ICC	BETO_0906	0.509	0.36	0.422
ICC	BETO_0406	0.487	0.349	0.406
Vicomtech NLP-team	meddopprof-joint	0.426	0.38	0.402
ICC	BETO_1006	0.487	0.271	0.348
Vicomtech NLP-team	semantic_mapping	0.26	0.254	0.257
Vicomtech NLP-team	semantic_mapping_version2	0.254	0.247	0.25
EdIE-KnowLab	T1BETO_positive	0.165	0.193	0.178
EdIE-KnowLab	T1BETO_positive_ProfNER	0.151	0.177	0.163
EdIE-KnowLab	T2BETO_positive	0.134	0.165	0.148